

Efficient flow monitoring for virtualized applications with eBPF

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Abstract—Flow monitoring is widely used to understand the composition of network traffic, which can be used to spot anomalies, attacks, misconfigurations. While dedicated hardware appliances are commonly used in physical infrastructures, efficient software implementations are today required for virtualized and software-defined systems, which are often designed to run in different environments. Traditionally, efficient packet processing in software requires is based on kernel-bypass mechanisms; this approach brings large performance gains, but requires additional kernel modules and the re-implementation of common functions of the standard networking stack.

In ASTRID, we investigated the usage of the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) for effective and efficient packet inspection. Our goal is the implementation of a lightweight flow-monitoring tool that provides similar information as existing appliances but with a reduced execution footprint, in order to be easily integrated in cloud-native applications. The scope is limited to basic flow identification, including most common fields in the IP, ICMP, TCP, and UDP headers, whereas Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) is currently out of the scope.

Index Terms—Network flow monitoring, cloud computing, eBPF, cloud-native applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Flow monitoring is widely used to understand the behavior of both local and wide area packet networks. It usually groups packet according to a common pattern based on the identification of the endpoints through 5 main parameters: source network address, destination network address, protocol, source transport port, and destination transport port. Despite the relative simplicity of this definition, network flow collection is a cumbersome process because all packets must be parsed in order to extract the relevant fields and to detect the begin/end of the flow. For this reason, typical implementations usually relies on dedicated hardware, sometimes integrated in the same network devices; in addition, sampling is largely used in case of high bitrate. Flow-level information can then be further processed and visualized by remote processes, and there are several protocols to exchange this information (NetFlow, IPFIX, sFlow).

With the growing adoption of softwarization and virtualization techniques, hardware appliances can be seldom used, because cloud applications are often designed to work in different environments. Besides, the amount of network traffic processed by a typical virtual service is not comparable with physical infrastructures. In case of network services, the solution is either to load balance the traffic among multiple

replicas of network functions, or to make usage of hardware acceleration functions offered by the underlying infrastructure.

By analyzing existing appliances for flow monitoring, we identified *nProbe*¹ and *Zeek*² as the most interesting tools, which target different usage scenarios. *nProbe* is basically a NetFlow/IPFIX-compatible flow exporter, with DPI capabilities and support for over 250 applications. *nProbe* is part of a larger suite, *ntopng*³, which also includes traffic analysis and visualization capabilities. It is not open-source, though there is a free version with some limitations on capabilities and usage. On the other hand, *Zeek* (formerly *Bro*) is fully open-source and it provides a flexible framework that is easy to extend. *Zeek* does not export flow descriptors, but it only creates compact transaction logs, file content, and fully customized output, suitable for manual review analyses by a Security and Information Event Management (SIEM) system. Therefore, both selected tools are not active security devices, rather they are conceived as monitoring agents.

Because of the long list of available DPI features and supported applications and protocols, these tools does not have a negligible resource footprint. This is perfectly acceptable when security analysis requires deep investigation, but it also results in large resource wasting when only basic information is required. For instance, it is quite common to apply Machine Learning algorithms on a reduced set of features [1], [2]. This effectively raises the problem of the unnecessary overhead in the execution of virtual services.

To address this issue, we designed and implemented *bpfflowmon*, leveraging the eBPF technology for flow monitoring. Our main objective was to understand if and to what extent the eBPF framework could be used for packet inspection, in order to derive common statistics and, in case, custom features. For this reason, the current implementation only considers the most common use-cases, by parsing IPv4/6, ICMP, TCP, and UDP headers. Extensions to further protocols, especially the support of more options and tunneling was left behind the preliminary performance and functional validation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We describe the main outcome of our work and claimed innovations in Sec. II. We provide a brief overview of other tools that already uses eBPF technology for monitoring and inspection in Sec. III, also pointing out the main different with our work. Then, we describe the *bpfflowmon* tool developed in ASTRID in Sec. IV. We report in Sec. V the results of the intensive

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¹<https://www.ntop.org/products/netflow/nprobe/>.

²<https://zeek.org/>.

³<https://www.ntop.org/>.

performance evaluation we carried out by comparing our tool with nProbe and Zeek. A brief overview of known limitations for the eBPF framework in general and our implementation is given in Sec. VI. We also provide a short survey of the current scientific literature about the usage of eBPF-based tools for security purposes in Sec. VII. Finally, we give our conclusion in Sec. VIII, which includes the road away.

II. ASTRID INNOVATIONS

One of the main objective for the ASTRID project was to follow an infrastructure-agnostic approach, hence giving more freedom to service operators about the selection of the environment(s) to run their applications. In this respect, we addressed the problem of monitoring network flows by software in a more effective way than existing tools.

In this respect, we designed and developed a new approach for flow monitoring, based on the usage of eBPF for packet inspection. Our tool is named `bpfflowmon` and is made of:

- an eBPF program attached to the `tc` hook, which builds a raw table of unidirectional flows, as seen on one or more network interfaces;
- a userland program that periodically scans the raw flow table, merges and removes terminated flows and exports them;
- a daemon for loading/unloading the eBPF and userland programs.

Our work therefore addresses the specific nature of cloud-native applications better than other existing tools. Once more, we highlight that our tool is not a replacement of existing appliances for DPI, but a more efficient alternative for a quite broad range of monitoring use-cases that only require basic flow statistics.

While chasing the general ASTRID objectives of creating lightweight agents and remaining infrastructure-agnostic, we achieved two **main innovations**: small execution footprint and portability.

A. Small execution footprint

When designing cloud-native applications, it is important to reduce the usage of CPU, memory and disk space to make the deployment process faster and to decrease the cost in case public cloud infrastructures are used. This allows to replicate the same agents without incurring in large overhead, which is useful when there is the need for intra-pod monitoring or cross-cloud deployments.

Our evaluation shows that CPU usage and memory footprint of our implementation are almost one order of magnitude lower than the selected alternatives, while reporting the same level of information. A small execution footprint saves computing and memory resources, yielding to lower Operating Expense (OpEx) and better performance for service providers.

B. Portability

On the other hand, **portability** allows to deploy the same application in different environments, including both private and public infrastructures, in this case lowering the Capital

Expenditure (CapEx) with respect to maintaining different software versions and widening the potential market.

Among the main concerns for flow monitoring there are the sustainable packet rate and the computing overhead. It is well known that most of the processing delay is due to packet copies, interrupt handling and context switches, therefore many approaches have been proposed to bypass the built-in kernel networking stack and to give direct access to hardware queues (e.g., `PF_RING`, `Netmap`, `DPDK`, `OpenOnLoad`). Unfortunately, all forwarding and processing operation must be realized in user-space, without any pre-defined structure or template, and this is a major drawback from the development perspective. In addition, the availability and effectiveness of such technologies in a virtualized environment is questionable, especially in the case of public infrastructures.

We ensure portability by building on standard kernel features only, without requiring additional hardware accelerators or kernel modules. Many packet processing tools (including nProbe and Zeek) make use of PFring and similar kernel extensions to increase performance. However, this feature is not build in the standard kernel. It is unlikely that this feature is available in any Kubernetes installation, hence jeopardizing its usage. All selected tool also run with PFring, but with meaningful performance degradation. Our approach only leverages the eBPF technology which is already built-in in any recent Linux kernel (4.19 and 5.x), which is the common options for all installations. This ensure predictable performance in environments provided by different providers, hence giving more freedom in the deployment and migration processes.

III. EBPF FOR MONITORING AND INSPECTION

Monitoring the behavior of an Operating System and its applications has always been a hot topic both for performance and security reasons. The scope can include applications in user space, the kernel, and even network traffic exchanged with external systems. Traditionally, security appliances can monitor the integrity of the file system, the behavior of the system users and other applications (by looking at logs), network flows originated, terminated, or proxied at the host. Support from the kernel is instead required to access packets in transit (e.g., in case of routers and software switches) and to gain visibility over internal operations of the same kernel, which may be the primary target of attacks. While consolidated practice and tools already exist to cover all different scopes, kernel monitoring has been based for long on third-party extensions; this approach requires to update and re-compile the modules every time the kernel changes, and brings the risk for introducing instability.

The eBPF framework mitigates existing issues for kernel monitoring by introducing a common interface to easily access multiple subsystems. It gives access to multiple data sources present in the kernel, by allowing to inject code at “probes” (kprobes/uprobes) and “tracepoints” (USDT/kernel tracepoints / `ltng-ust`), as well as at “network hooks” (XDP, TC). The framework allows to write programs in C code, which are then attached to specific hooks into the running kernel, after the eBPF verifier has checked they are loop-free and do

not access data outside of their boundary. Data collected by such programs can be stored in shared data structures (*maps*) between the kernel and the user-space, where other programs are responsible to process them or to deliver them to external applications. Developing eBPF applications is not trivial for beginners, but common operations are available through more user-friendly frontends, like the BPF Compiler Collection (BCC).⁴

A key added-value of eBPF is that it does not require a new kernel module in comparison to other tools (e.g. LTTng or SystemTap). Though it was originally conceived for investigating performance issues, eBPF is also valuable for security monitoring, network filtering as well as for program tracing, profiling, and debugging (see the many examples discussed in Sec. VII). Indeed, many commercial and open-source frameworks have already integrated eBPF, including Suricata⁵, Sysdig Falco⁶, Cilium⁷. While Suricata and Falco are mostly concerned with monitoring, Cilium uses eBPF to provide secure network connectivity and load balancing, leveraging the ability of eBPF to filter and drop packets based on rules. Interestingly, eBPF can trace kernel functions but cannot drop their execution, whereas this is instead possible for network packets. For observability, ntop and InfluxData have partnered to offer eBPF monitoring for containers, while Netdata is offering out-of-the-box eBPF monitoring for system and application monitoring⁸.

Similar to ASTRID objectives, Cilium leverages eBPF in a cloud native and micro-services context. Kubectl-trace is a Kubernetes command line front end for running bpfftrace across worker machines in Kubernetes cluster. However, to the best of our knowledge there is no solution yet to activate metric capturing during the deployment of a containerized application with Kubernetes or equivalent [3].

IV. THE ASTRID TOOL: BPFLOWMON

The overall structure of our eBPF-based flow monitoring implementation is sketched in Fig. 1. The `bpfflowmon` framework includes different components, which are partially run in the kernel and partially in user space. The source code is available in github, together with a minimal guide for using the software.⁹

The `tc_flowmon_kern.ko` is the eBPF code loaded into the kernel. It can be attached both to the ingress and egress queue of any network interface. If the virtual function is behaving like a router or switch, the program should be installed in a single direction, otherwise forwarded packets will be counted twice. If the function is not forwarding packets, a program must be installed on each direction, to monitor both incoming and outgoing packets. If multiple interfaces are present, the program could be installed on one or more

Fig. 1. Software architecture of `bpfflowmon`.

of them, even if the current implementation only allows the selection of a single or all interfaces.¹⁰

The implementation of the `tc_flowmon_kern.ko` module is rather simple, according to the specific nature of eBPF programs. It is basically a parser of network packets, starting from Ethernet up to TCP/UDP headers. As already noted beforehand, this preliminary implementation was mostly conceived for performance investigation, so the support for additional protocols and deep-packet inspection are left for future extensions. Such extensions would also require a more complex design, since we already reached the size limit of the small stack available to eBPF programs. A possible solution could be to split the parsing framework into multiple programs, and to chain them with the *tail call* mechanism. This is not expected to increase significantly the processing delay, since additional programs are only called when the specific protocols are present. An alternative approach could be to forward only a subset of relevant data to the userspace, similarly to Zeek. This would let user to write their own policies in a simpler way, but would likely increase resource usage.

The behavior of `tc_flowmon_kern.ko` follows common practice for flow analysis. Each flow is identified by the 5-tuple $\langle src_ip_addr, dst_ip_addr, proto, src_port, dst_port \rangle$, where the last two parameters are only present where applicable.¹¹ We point out that this definition identifies “unidirectional” flows; in general, for each *forward-direction* flow $\langle addr1, addr2, proto, port1, port2 \rangle$ there will always be a *backward-direction* flow $\langle addr2, addr1, proto, port2, port1 \rangle$ with IP addresses and protocol ports inverted. Our eBPF program only works on unidirectional flows and stores them in a shared map, but it does not merge them, since this operation would be time consuming and useless at this level. Therefore, each time a packet is received, the corresponding flow is inferred from its header and it is created in the shared map if not present.

For each flow, data is kept that provides all NetFlow/IPFIX flow information elements as nProbe regarding IP and UDP/TCP fields;¹² other metadata concerning routing information, BGP domains, inspection engine, DNS resolution are not taken into account because they could be more efficiently

⁴<https://github.com/iovisor/bcc>.

⁵<https://suricata.readthedocs.io/en/latest/capture-hardware/ebpf-xdp.html>.

⁶<https://sysdig.com/blog/sysdig-and-falco-now-powered-by-ebpf/>.

⁷<https://cilium.io/>.

⁸<https://containerjournal.com/topics/container-management/using-ebpf-monitoring-to-know-what-to-measure-and-why/>.

⁹https://github.com/mattereppe/bpf_flowmon.

¹⁰This simplification is done on purpose in this alpha version of the code, because monitoring a subset of interfaces would give limited visibility on flows using the unmonitored interfaces.

¹¹Indeed, the *src_port* field is used with a different meaning for ICMP protocol, to identify the message type.

¹²https://www.ntop.org/guides/nprobe/flow_information_elements.html.

managed in the user space (indeed, this is not done because they look less useful for the purpose of network analytics). Table I summarizes the supported fields at the time of writing; the objective is to make them easily extendable as the work progresses.

The second building block of the `bpfflowmon` framework is the `tc_flowmon_user` utility. This is a C program running in user-space that periodically scans the shared map of unicast flows, merge them, dump and remove terminated flows. The usage of the C language instead of the BCC framework is mostly motivated by the need for more efficiency, especially with a large number of flows. This approach slightly complicates the development work, because of the usage of a lower-level programming language, but it is almost transparent to the user, which only has the additional task to compile the framework before running it.

The separation between packet inspection and flow management perfectly fits the design pattern for eBPF programs, leading to an efficient approach. As common practice for this problem, flows are considered terminated either after explicit messages (FIN or RST flags have been seen for TCP) or an inactivity timeout (which works for both TCP, UDP, and ICMP). The choice of the inactivity timeout affects the precision of flow identification; this parameter is configurable as for similar tools. When two unidirectional flows are merged together, the result is a bidirectional flow which source is conventionally assumed according to the first packet seen; informative elements are then kept separate for the forward and backward direction, since this is a typical requirement from analytics and detection algorithms. This represent an extension with respect to, e.g., `nProbe`, which only provides aggregate metrics for both directions. The current version dumps flows to text files (or to the standard output), either in plaintext or JSON format.

Finally, the last component is the management script `tc_flowmon.sh`, which takes care of loading the eBPF programs and starting the userland utility. It support all the necessary options to select the eBPF program and its entry point, the interfaces to monitor, and user-space options (polling parameters, filename and folder for dumping, etc.). Though the same functions performed by `tc_flowmon.sh` could be easily integrated into the userland utility, this approach has been preferred for the development and investigation phase because of the easier maintenance of the different components. Further, it simplifies the integration with `SysVinit` and `Systemd` for automatically starting and stopping the whole framework.

V. EVALUATION

Evaluation of the proposed approach was carried out by comparing both how precision and performance vary with respect to existing tools. In the first case, we investigated if and under what conditions there are deviations in the detected flows with respect to `nProbe`. In the second case, we compared the maximum transfer rate and the overhead in terms of resource consumption, including both CPU time and memory with respect to *i*) the baseline scenario (where no monitoring tool is run), *ii*) to `nProbe`, and *iii*) to `Zeek`.

TABLE I
INFORMATION ELEMENTS FOR `bpfflowmon`.

Name	Context	Meaning
<code>first_seen</code>	General	Epoch of the first packet of this flow (ns).
<code>last_seen</code>	General	Epoch of the last packet seen so far (ns).
<code>jitter</code>	General	Cumulative delays between packets.
<code>pkts</code>	General	Cumulative number of packets.
<code>ifindex</code>	General	Capture interface.
<code>version</code>	IP	Version (4/6)
<code>tos</code>	IP	TOS/DSCP (IPv4) or Traffic Class (IPv6).
<code>fl</code>	IP	Flow label (IPv6).
<code>bytes</code>	IP	Cumulative number of bytes.
<code>min_pkt_len</code>	IP	Smallest IP packet seen in the flow.
<code>max_pkt_len</code>	IP	Biggest IP packet seen in the flow.
<code>pkt_size_hist[6]</code>	IP	[0]: pkts up to 128 bytes; [1]: pkts from 128 to 256 bytes; [2]: pkts from 256 to 512 bytes; [3]: pkts from 512 to 1024 bytes; [4]: pkts from 1024 to 1514 bytes; [5]: pkts over 1514 bytes.
<code>min_ttl</code>	IP	Min TTL (IPv4) or Hop Limit (IPv6).
<code>max_ttl</code>	IP	Max TTL (IPv4) or Hop Limit (IPv6).
<code>pkt_ttl_hist[10]</code>	IP	[0]: pkts with TTL=1; [1]: pkts with TTL>1 and TTL ≤ 5; [2]: packets with TTL > 5 and ≤ 32; [3]: packets with TTL > 32 and ≤ 64; [4]: packets with TTL > 64 and ≤ 96; [5]: packets with TTL > 96 and ≤ 128; [6]: packets with TTL > 128 and ≤ 160; [7]: packets with TTL > 160 and ≤ 192; [8]: packets with TTL > 192 and ≤ 224; [9]: packets with TTL > 224 and ≤ 255.
<code>next_seq</code>	TCP	Last sequence number seen (used for computing retransmissions).
<code>last_id</code>	TCP	Last ipv4 identification value for <code>last_seq</code> .
<code>cumulative_flags</code>	TCP	Cumulative TCP flags seen in all packets so far.
<code>retr_pkts</code>	TCP	Total number of retrasmited packets.
<code>retr_bytes</code>	TCP	Total number of retrasmited bytes.
<code>ooo_pkts</code>	TCP	Total number of out-of-order packets.
<code>ooo_bytes</code>	TCP	Total number of out-of-order bytes.
<code>min_win_bytes</code>	TCP	Min TCP Window.
<code>max_win_bytes</code>	TCP	Max TCP Window.
<code>mss</code>	TCP	TCP Max Segment Size.
<code>wndw_scale</code>	TCP	TCP Window Scale.

TABLE II
CONFIGURATION OF OPENSTACK SERVERS USED FOR TESTING.

Node	vCores	vRAM	vStorage
Sender	1	1 GB	16 GB
Receiver	1	1 GB	16 GB
Forwarder	4	2 GB	32 GB

Since our main application target is virtualized services, we performed our experiments in Virtual Machines (VMs). In this way we can account for any limitations that packet acceleration software experiences in virtualized environments. We didn't run the software in containers, because this is not expected to bring to different results as far as resources assigned to the containers are not limited.

Evaluation was carried out under the same testbed topology built in an OpenStack installation: one sender that generates packets, one receiver that performs measurements, one intermediate node that runs the flow monitoring tool. Flows were monitored on both interfaces of the intermediate node, which is a typical condition in case multiple interfaces are present. All nodes ran on the same hypervisor, 2x Intel Xeon CPU E5-2660 v4@2.00GHz with 14 cores and hyperthreading enabled, 128 GB RAM, 64 GB SSD storage. The configuration of the three OpenStack servers is reported in Table II.

For precision analysis, we used Pcap traces available from the Internet, which include a mix of ICMP, TCP and UDP traffic. More specifically, we used two network traces of different size designed to test IPFIX/NetFlow, indicated as smallFlows and bigFlows.¹³ For performance we generated network packets with iperf3,¹⁴ while varying the main parameters that might affect the inspection process.

A. Precision

We investigated if and how the flows detected by `bpfflowmon` differ from what reported by `nProbe`. Indeed, the two tools performs almost the same way, and most differences are only due to different configuration settings. For instance, the flow inactivity timeout, namely the time to wait without seeing any packet before considering the flow closed, largely affects the reporting. With a small value, the risk is that a single flow is seen as two separate flows, when there the gap between the transmission of consecutive packets is large enough. On the other hand, with a large value the risk is that two independent flows are seen as the same conversation; however, this is unlikely with TCP, because the end of the connection is also detected by the header flags (both in case of normal closing and aborting/resetting).

In the following, we summarize our main findings for different protocols.

1) *ICMP*: Notably, `bpfflowmon` uses the ICMP Type field as source port (even if this may look like an abuse of the classification), so it distinguishes between different ICMP flows involving the same couple of peers. Instead, `nProbe` sets

¹³Both traces are available at <https://tcpreplay.appneta.com/wiki/captures.html>.

¹⁴<https://iperf.fr/>.

both protocol source and destination ports to 0, hence failing to give indication about the type of ICMP messages.

From our experiments, `bpfflowmon` successfully correlates ICMP requests with responses, while the same behavior is not guaranteed for `nProbe` (we observe several cases where two separate flows are reported).¹⁵

2) *TCP*: Resetting a TCP connection might have side effects, because this operation does not usually imply mutual agreement from the peers. The challenging aspect is that multiple reset packets may be sent, in case the remote peer continues to acknowledge previous packets. Under this (not so uncommon) circumstance, `nProbe` terminates the flow on the first reset, so any following reset/ack packet is accounted as a different flow. Our implementation partially mitigates this problem, because the userland utility only dumps a flow after scanning the map of unidirectional flows, which happens periodically. This way, any additional (re-)transmission in a short timeframe is counted as part of the previous flow.¹⁶ This largely avoids the incorrect reporting of tiny flows with a few ack/reset packets.

In a similar way, it is possible that duplicated packets are received after the exchange of FIN messages, and get counted as different flows. In this case, the problem was observed for `bpfflowmon`, due to the fact that the map of active flows was scanned just after the exchange of FIN messages.¹⁷ The problem could be easily solved by waiting for the inactive timeout before purging the flows, but this brings two drawbacks: i) the dumping is delayed (and this may be a problem, if we are trying to identify malicious flows in real-time), and ii) two consecutive flows might be merged together (the split between user and kernel space tasks does not allow to easily take into account the presence of two consecutive flows with the same 5-tuple).

3) *UDP*: We didn't observe relevant differences between `nProbe` and `bpfflowmon` for UDP traffic, but we noticed a potential flaw with source routing. As a matter of fact, both `nProbe` and `bpfflowmon` are transparent to the source routing option, so they are somehow cheated because they only see the "inner" intermediate node and not the final destination of the packet. This means that if only part of packets belonging to the same flow are sent with the loose source routing option, whereas the remaining are not, `bpfflowmon` reports two separate flows (and `nProbe` does the same).¹⁸ This, in some way, affects the statistics of traffic towards given destinations.

In this case, we used a third tool to better investigate this problem, namely `tshark`, the terminal-based version of `Wireshark`. Interestingly, this tool is able to parse the full range of options and reports a single flow towards the correct destination, as after all `Wireshark` does too.

4) *SNMP*: We found another unexpected behavior in case of SNMP flows. This time, the oddity was found for `tshark`,

¹⁵This is the case, for instance, for packets numbered 108593 and 108755 (according to `Wireshark`) in the bigFlows trace.

¹⁶This happens, for instance, for TCP stream number 19032 (as reported by `Wireshark`), again from the bigFlows trace.

¹⁷This was observed for TCP stream number 16749 (as reported by `Wireshark`), again from the bigFlows trace.

¹⁸This was observed for UDP stream 1164 (according to `Wireshark` numbering), from the bigFlows trace.

which reported two separate UDP flows for the same SNMP conversation, even if also Wireshark grouped the messages in the same flow.¹⁹ We guess this might be due to some interpretation of the SNMP, but we didn't investigate the issue in detail because deep packet inspection is out of scope for our work and our tool behaves well in this scenario.

B. Performance and overhead

Performance and overhead were investigated by considering both the impact on packet transmission as well as resource consumption. We considered both UDP and TCP flows, by varying the main parameters that are expected to affect packet processing:

- packet size and transmission rate for UDP flows;
- maximum segment size (MSS) for TCP streams.

For packet size, we considered 4 values that are representative of the following cases:

- 16 bytes is the smallest value allowed by iperf, and this is the worst condition for packet forwarding;
- 1470 bytes is representative of the biggest Ethernet packets, also accounting for the presence of tunneling in the underlying virtual network;
- 8192 bytes is the reference size for jumbo frames in Ethernet, which is a common situation in all installations;
- 65507 bytes is the maximum size allowed by UDP and the best condition for packet forwarding, but it is only feasible on loopback interfaces (therefore, it can only be used when VMs are running on the same host).

For the transmission rate, we considered a broad range of different load conditions, from 10 Kbps to the unfeasible (at least for our installation) rate of 10 Gbps. For the MSS, we again selected 4 values that this time are representative of: the smallest value accepted by iperf3 (88 bytes), the minimum value that should be used on IP links (536 bytes), the typical value used for Ethernet links (1460 bytes) and jumbo frames (8192 bytes).

The comparison considered two flavors of nProbe, with or without PF_RING, and Zeek. When using PF_RING, nProbe can inspect packets from multiple interfaces, but a separate instance must be run for each interface when the accelerator is not used, with clear impact on resource usage. In addition, we assumed the transmission without flow monitoring tools as the “baseline”, which is the best value we can achieve in the target scenario, without the usage of accelerators and other tailored modifications of the vanilla OpenStack installation.

To make the comparison fair, we collected the same set of information fields (IP protocol version, IP source and destination addressed, L4 protocol, L4 source and destination ports, flow start/end timestamp, flow duration, forward/backward packets, forward/backward bytes), and we dumped the information to file. Experiments were run for 10 minutes each, so to mitigate as much as possible interference with other parallel activity, both in the network and within the guest/host systems.

¹⁹This happens for UDP stream 3604 (again, according to Wireshark numbering), bearing an SNMP conversation from the bigFlows trace.

Fig. 2. Measured bitrate at the receiver, while varying packet size and the transmission bitrate for a UDP flow.

Fig. 3. Measured packet loss at the receiver, while varying packet size and the transmission bitrate for a UDP flow.

1) *Impact on packet transmission:* Our analysis focuses on the parameters reported by iperf3, namely the transmission rate, packet error rate and jitter. Fig. 2 shows how the measured bitrate at the receiver changes for different settings of packet size and transmission bitrate for UDP flows. There are not meaningful differences between the different mechanisms, even if nProbe with PF_RING performs slightly better in case of bigger packets.

Fig. 3 measures the percentage packet loss at the receiver under the same conditions. As expected, packet loss is higher with smaller packet size and higher transmission rate. Both bpfflowmon and nProbe without PF_RING perform almost the same way as the baseline scenario, whereas the behavior of nProbe with PF_RING and Zeek is much more unpredictable. Zeek seems to perform better than other tools almost in all conditions, but it suffers a packet loss close to 100% in case of 65507-bytes packets at the fastest transmission rate. We do not have a clear motivation for this anomaly, but for sure it is persistent across many replicas of the experiment.

The last UDP measurement is the average packet jitter, shown in Fig. 4. The variation in the inter-packet delay is negligible for practical applications (below 0.1 ms), and it is likely to be highly affected by external factors (including

Fig. 4. Measured packet jitter at the receiver, while varying packet size and the transmission bitrate for a UDP flow.

Fig. 5. Measured bitrate at the receiver, while varying the MSS for a TCP flow.

perturbations in the generator and the receiver). Similarly to previous indexes, there is no tool which wins over all in every condition.

Oddly, in the baseline scenario we achieved worse performance than with flow monitoring, and this is rather unexpected, especially when compared to `bpfflowmon` and `nProbe` without `PF_RING`. We do not think these are measurement errors, since the same behavior is present in all conditions and occurred even when replicating the experiments.

Finally, we show in Fig. 5 the transmission rate achievable by TCP when generating packets for the whole duration of the experiment. Not surprisingly, higher bitrate are possible with larger MSS, because this has a beneficial impact on the TCP flow control mechanism. Again, no meaningful differences are visible between the different tools, even if in this case the baseline scenario achieves slightly higher bitrate, in line with what expected.

By looking at the performance indexes reported in this Section, we can conclude that our eBPF-based mechanism does not affect packet transmission in a significant way.

2) *CPU usage*: CPU and memory usage are important to understand what is the impact on the operation of other applications and to find the correct size for the containers

TABLE III
MEMORY SIZE FOR KERNEL MODULES USED BY FLOW MONITORING TOOLS.

Name	Size [kB]
<code>pf_ring</code>	737.280
<code>cls_bpf</code>	24.576

that will host the monitoring tool. We expect significant differences in the usage of CPU between `bpfflowmon` and the other tools, due to the different architectural design. As a matter of fact, `Zeek` and `nProbe` are basically user-space applications. The default capture driver for `Zeek` is `libpcap`,²⁰ whereas `nProbe` builds on the `PF_RING` module in kernel space, falling back to `libpcap` if `PF_RING` is not available. On the other hand, our `bpfflowmon` tool leverages in-kernel eBPF programs, hence the usage of CPU from kernel and userspace is expected to be rather different.

This is largely confirmed by the measurements reported in Fig. 6 for a UDP flow, which show much higher CPU usage for user-space in case of `nProbe` and `Zeek`. However, there is not a corresponding saving in CPU usage by the kernel, probably due to the usage of polling mechanism in both `PF_RING` and `libpcap` (please note the logarithm scale is used in this case).

A more detailed breakdown of CPU usage confirms that most time is spent in kernel and user-mode rather than other states. Fig. 7 shows that `bpfflowmon` always brings a small overhead with respect to the baseline. In case of `nProbe`, the usage of `PF_RING` has a bad impact with low traffic, again because of the need for polling. When the traffic increases, the benefit of `PF_RING` is evident, but the total overhead is still far beyond our eBPF-based tool.

Similar considerations hold in case of TCP, which measurements are shown in Fig. 8 and 9.

3) *Memory allocation*: When comparing the two tools, the first thing to consider is the need for additional kernel modules. Indeed, `nProbe` requires the `pf_ring` kernel module (which is proprietary and not released as open-source), whereas `bpfflowmon` needs the `cls_bpf` module (which is part of the vanilla kernel); `Zeek` does not require any kernel extension (even if `PF_RING` support is available as option). Table III shows that the size of the `pf_ring` modules is much larger than for `cls_bpf`.

Going on, the next step is memory consumption in user space. For each user-space application, we considered the Virtual Memory Size (VMS, virtual memory also accounting for external libraries), Resident Set Size (RSS, namely the actual size of physical memory, again including shared libraries), Proportional Set Size (PSS, namely the size of physical memory with proportional attribution of shared libraries), and Anonymous (the stack and other allocations not mapped to files). Fig. 10 shows that `nProbe` has a higher VMS consumption with respect to our tool, but `Zeek` is far beyond any other tools. We remark one more time that this is largely due to the many features available in these applications; in

²⁰There are alternative capture drivers that can be used with `Zeek`, including raw sockets, `libpcap`, and `PF_RING`. We only considered `libpcap` in our study.

(a) Kernel

(b) User

Fig. 6. CPU usage measured at the intermediate node, while varying the packet size and transmission bitrate for a UDP flow.

(a) 16-bytes payload

(b) 1470-bytes payload

(c) 8192-bytes payload

(d) 65507-bytes payload

Fig. 7. Cumulative CPU usage measured at the intermediate node, for a UDP flow.

Fig. 8. CPU usage measured at the intermediate node, while varying the MSS for a TCP flow.

Fig. 9. Cumulative CPU usage measured at the intermediate node, for a TCP flow.

Fig. 10. Memory allocation for the different user-space tools.

general, we do not say this allocation is disproportionate to what the application does, but simply it is not efficient when only simple measurements are needed. However, the RSS of Zeek and nProbe is comparable, even if still much larger than our implementation.

Notably, memory allocation almost doubles when PF_RING is not used. The reason is that nProbe can only monitor one network interface, so to keep the comparison functionally equivalent with the other cases we have to run two parallel instances, one for each interface. This is necessary to see all traffic intended to the host, but unfortunately all forwarded traffic will be accounted twice in this case. If additional network interfaces are monitored, the memory usage will scale accordingly. The same issue applies to Zeek: in this case, we do not have to manually start two instances, but they are anyway launched when multiple interfaces are selected in the configuration file.

VI. LIMITATIONS OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The eBPF framework represents an efficient alternative for monitoring and inspection than existing tools, especially for virtualized environments. However, both our preliminary implementations and the framework in general are not exempt from limitations that devote further investigation in the future.

One main drawback of eBPF programs is the limited stack size available, which limits the number of functions and instructions. Though the original stack size of 512 bytes may be extended in future releases, parsing several network layers remains a challenging issue, especially when variable options are present. We were able to parse common fields in IPv4/IPv6/UDP/TCP headers, but inspecting all TCP options requires at least to drop support for one IP version. To overcome this limitation, next releases of bpf_flowmon will leverage the *tail call* mechanism, which allow to invoke a chain of eBPF programs. This approach would bring the opportunity for deep packet inspection, and it is also expected to improve the flexibility and composability of the system, as new parsers can be easily added to the base framework.

Another well-known drawback is the eBPF verifier that, on the one hand ensures there are no loops and the program always terminates, but on the other hand still has many limitations, including high rate of false positives, poor scalability, and lack of support for loops [4]. As a matter of fact, the verifier does not scale to programs with a large number of paths, its algorithm is not formally specified, and no formal argument about its correctness is given; indeed, multiple bugs have been already discovered.²¹ Programmers have to “infer” the way that the verifier performs sanity checks, for their code to be accepted. Indeed, developers often waste a lot of time for this process, e.g., by inserting redundant sanity checks on pointers. This definitely represents a major barrier for quickly extending the framework, especially when parsing headers with a number of variable options. A better verifier, grounded in state-of-the-art verification theory and practice, would enable a wider range of eBPF use cases and would dramatically simplify the development process.

VII. RELATED WORK

Deri et al. [5] note that existing monitoring and tracing tools (Sysdig, Falco, Cilium) mostly lack the ability to match network with system events in order to provide complete visibility both at system and network level, while preventing unwanted network communications to take place similar to what IPSs currently do. Based on this consideration, they extend their existing tool *ntopng* with events generated by *libebpf*, a library that enriches network-layer data (e.g. source and destination IP addresses) with system metadata (e.g. source and destination processes and system users). Their objective is to support the definition of custom policies to drop unwanted connections, by affecting the return value of the kernel functions that are used to create network flows. However the Linux kernel supports override returns only on a small group of functions, which does not include the ones concerning network activities. For this reason, the kernel has been patched to enable this mechanism for network communications. A major limitation of this approach is that only local processes and users are visible through eBPF. As a future work, small eBPF probes will be created and disseminated in the network with the aim of circumventing this limitation and have visibility also on remote clients and servers.

eBPF can be used to break up the conventional packet filtering model in Linux, moving the inspection process in the XDP, where ingress traffic can be processed before the allocation of kernel data structures which comes along with performance benefits [6]. This provides a first line of defense against traffic that is in general unwanted by the host, e.g., spoofed addresses or Denial-of-Service flooding attacks [7]. Indeed, independent studies have shown that XDP can yield four times the performance in comparison to performing a similar task in the kernel using common packet filtering tools [8], and can be even integrated with existing well-known management interfaces (i.e., iptables) [9]. This approach is made even more interesting given that dedicated platforms for packet filter offloading based on FPGAs like HyPaFilter

[10] and hXDP [11] or SmartNICs supporting eBPF [12] have emerged.

In the context of network tracing, Suo et al. [13] propose a framework where a master node translates user inputs into configuration files, eBPF agents are used to monitor network packets of specific connections at given tracepoints (e.g., virtual network interfaces), and measurements are centrally collected and analyzed. vNetTracer supports instrumenting kernel functions, return of kernel functions, kernel tracepoints and raw sockets through kprobe, kretprobe, tracepoints and network devices, hence providing a monitoring tool that works across the boundary of single domains.

In [14] the authors propose an eBPF-based implementation for duplicating packets at the OpenvSwitch. They tackle the use case of monitoring the traffic between VMs without specific hardware appliances for duplicating packets. Their analysis shows that duplicating packets with an eBPF program in the `tc` hook achieves better throughput than native Port Mirroring of OpenvSwitch, especially in case of large packets.

Cassagnes et al. [3] designed a system for deploying eBPF programs and collect their measurements in containerized user-space applications. They used tools like Prometheus, Performance Co-Pilot, and Vector, and developed specific eBPF programs and their userland counterparts for monitoring the garbage collector, identifying HTTP traffic, and IP whitelisting. Nevertheless, they are only able to spot local information, and a global end-to-end view on distributed applications is still missing.

Beyond monitoring and tracing, eBPF has also been used to create programmable data planes in the kernel, in order to overcome the common difficulty in maintaining kernel modules and pushing the code in the main upstream kernel version. The main objective has typically been the realization of more network functions in the kernel, to achieve better performance, without sacrificing its generality. The combination of eBPF programs for the data plane with user-space helpers and control functions has been the common denominator for the work of several researchers [15]–[17].

eBPF programs can also be used to better support the integration of security features in containers. An example is the integration between Cilium and the Istio framework. The service mesh architecture of Istio requires all network traffic for both incoming and outgoing requests of all pods participating in the service mesh to be redirected to the sidecar proxy. The sidecar proxy will terminate all TCP connections and perform services such as telemetry, retries, routing, mutual TLS, and authorization on behalf of the services and use a secondary so-called upstream TCP connection to reach the destination service. This is what allows a service mesh to perform mutual TLS on behalf of the application and is what achieves the transparency to not require changing any application code when running a service mesh. However, this redirection can be costly when standard IP-based tooling such as iptables is used to implement the redirection as the entire TCP/IP stack has to be traversed multiple times. Cilium makes use of an exciting BPF feature called sockmap. It allows filtering and redirection at the socket level and is thus making Cilium socket-aware. The socket is the interface that

²¹<https://www.openwall.com/lists/oss-security/2017/12/21/2>.

applications use to send and receive network traffic. Applied to Istio redirection requirements, this allows to essentially short-circuit TCP sockets on the same node and thus massively accelerate the TCP connection between the application and the sidecar proxy of the service mesh in a completely transparent manner. Neither the application nor the sidecar proxy require modification in any way.²²

A less common use-case for eBPF technology is demonstrated by Baidya et al. for video transmission at the edge [18]. In this case, eBPF programs are used to duplicate packets and deliver them to multiple applications in order to avoid multi-unicast transmissions.

In [4], the authors propose an efficient verification algorithm for real-world eBPF programs that would overcome the limitations of the current verifier. The algorithm supports existing and emerging eBPF use cases and uses the framework of abstract interpretation. Their evaluation shows that the proposed abstraction is both precise and efficient for real-world eBPF programs.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed an alternative approach for network flow monitoring, based on eBPF technology. Our work was mainly motivated by the need for efficient yet effective solutions for virtualized environments, where hardware/software acceleration techniques are not available or largely ineffective, and resource usage is a performance and cost matter.

The extensive performance and functional validation demonstrated that our tool works as well as other more traditional approaches, but with a far smaller resource utilization footprint. Indeed, almost the same set of information elements is available for L3/L4 headers as state-of-the-art solutions, but with great savings in terms of CPU usage and memory allocation.

We do not claim that our `bpfflowmon` outperforms `nProbe` and `Zeek`, especially in terms of functionality and absolute performance for physical systems. However, we have demonstrated that a more lightweight approach is possible, especially for monitoring the traffic of virtualized applications in public cloud infrastructures.

There are a number of aspects that we are considering as part of our future research work. First of all, the aforementioned architectural change, from one single program to multiple programs linked by the tail call mechanism. Additionally, sending kinds of “events” to the user-space will allow to make custom processing; in this respect, it would be useful to consider possible integration with the `Zeek` framework.

Another optimization under investigation is to leverage header parsing already integrated in the kernel. Indeed, eBPF is not conceived for packet processing only, but it could be triggered by entry/exit points of kernel functions. Therefore, it would be useful to attach eBPF programs to some function which already parses the Ethernet/IP headers, as in the case of `libebpf`; unfortunately, parsing other protocols would still

be necessary in most cases (especially in case of forwarded packets).

Beyond specific aspects related to the eBPF technology, the current userland utility is rather limited in terms of export interfaces. It only dumps flows to file, both in plaintext and JSON; this can be easily composed with other ASTRID agents (`FileBeat`, `Logstash`) for sending data to the centralized platform, but it would also increase the overhead. Exporting data directly to Kafka is an additional feature that is worth integrating in the next release.

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